

Spatial and temporal microseismic evolution and surface subsidence during the deepest room and pillar trial test in the world

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Abstract

The depletion of coal reserves accessible by conventional longwall mining in Czech mines enabled testing a modified 'room and pillar' (R&P) method to extract high-grade coal from a large shaft protection pillar at a depth of 900 m, making this site one of the deepest R&P operations globally. The shaft pillar was divided into panels, developed with a bolter miner using galleries of 5.2×3.5 m, creating oblique and inclined pillars of 860–1225 m². The trial aimed to verify R&P feasibility at great depth while minimising surface subsidence, in contrast to longwall mining, which typically causes significant surface deformation. Precise monitoring of induced seismicity during R&P mining (without depillaring) provided a unique case study. Two groups of anomalous seismic responses were identified: (1) events occurring as R&P roadways approached old workings, particularly during pillar completion, and (2) increased activity near tectonic structures, mainly thrust faults, activated by roadway development, generating numerous events over a wide area. Ground surface stability was assessed via direct measurements of roadway roof subsidence and vertical displacement measurements at surface control points. Subsidence analysis indicated that pillar compression caused the largest surface subsidence of 17 mm due to R&P mining effect. Theoretical predictions of surface influence were validated against measured roof subsidence and empirical propagation calculations.

Keywords: Room and Pillar, Induced Seismicity, Great Depth, Surface

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Underground coal mining remains one of the most dangerous of all work
3 environments. One of the most useful ways of observing or predicting areas of
4 potential rockburst hazard within the rock mass in which mining operations
5 are located is to monitor seismological activity [1]. It is important to identify
6 the part of the rock mass where there is a higher number of high-energy
7 tremors, or the part with a specific local accumulation of low- and high-
8 energy seismic events [2]. Previously unused mining method in the Czech
9 part of the Upper Silesian Coal Basin (USCB), the 'room and pillar' (R&P)
10 method has been designed and prepared for initial testing.

11 The R&P mining method, as presented here, was used for the first time
12 in 200 years of history of coal mining in the southern part of the USCB.
13 The mining site selected for this trial was the deepest R&P mining site in
14 the world, with a depth of approximately 850–900 m below the surface. A
15 shaft safety pillar in the CSM mine in the stratigraphic position of coal seam
16 No. 30 was selected for testing of the R&P method, since this part of rock
17 mass (in both the vertical and horizontal directions) was evaluated as an area
18 without rockburst risk, based on a regional rockburst prognosis.

19 With a knowledge of the local conditions, and to ensure the safety of the
20 workers and the mining technology, a seismic monitoring system was pro-
21 posed as one part of rockburst prevention system. This system was designed
22 based on three geophysical subsystems that are normally used to monitor
23 seismic activity during longwall mining. Data were collected from the first
24 test mining site over more than three years of operation, and the final results
25 were used for a complex evaluation of the impact of the mining method on the
26 rock mass during and after the creation of pillars, in order to ensure a safer
27 working environment. The main goal of the trial test of the R&P method
28 was to show that the use of this mining method (which involves the creation
29 of pillars due to driving of roadways without subsequent de-pillaring of the
30 created pillars) rather than longwall mining has a very low impact on the
31 surface in terms of subsidence. The first results of seismological monitoring
32 were published after the extraction of the first R&P panel [3]. Presented
33 paper follow the first results [4] and presents a complex view of the seismic
34 activity during the mining of two R&P panels extended about subsidence
35 observed at the surface during testing of the R&P method.

36 Microseismic surveys presented in the past Schreiber et al. [3], Ellenberger
37 et al. [5], Luo et al. [6], Swanson et al. [7], Leake et al. [8] or Descour and
38 Miller [9] have verified that microseismic monitoring is a useful tool for un-
39 derstanding stress redistribution in an underground coal mine setting. Most
40 prior studies have analysed the seismicity induced by longwall mining, and
41 only two published studies have analysed the seismic activity associated with
42 R&P retreat mining. Both longwall and R&P retreat mining allow the over-
43 burden rock mass to cave. Only one study [3] involving monitoring of the
44 seismicity induced during R&P mining without depillaring has been pub-
45 lished before now.

46 Subsidence in R&P coal mining operations, even in cases where pillar re-
47 covery is not undertaken, remains an inherently intricate phenomenon. The
48 long-term stability of these excavations is critically dependent on the struc-
49 tural integrity of the load-bearing pillars that are left in place to uphold
50 the overlying strata [10]. Initial strategies for anticipating ground deforma-
51 tion were predominantly empirical [11], and relied on site observations and
52 relationships involving parameters such as the depth of extraction and lay-
53 out geometry [10]. Although useful, these approaches often fell short when
54 applied to heterogeneous geological settings.

55 A more rigorous analytical approach emerged through the adoption of
56 functional models, which facilitated a more systematic representation of
57 ground subsidence processes [11]. These methodologies included profile curve
58 fitting [12] and the influence function technique, as elaborated by Sroka et al.
59 [13] and further applied by Guzy and Witkowski [14], and offered enhanced
60 predictive capabilities by quantifying the subsidence effects that were at-
61 tributable to individual extraction zones.

62 The advent of numerical simulation marked a significant development
63 in the understanding of subsurface deformation. Computational techniques
64 such as the Finite Element Method (FEM) and Finite Difference Method
65 (FDM) enabled detailed examinations of the stress redistribution patterns
66 and the mechanical response of the surrounding rock mass, enabling the
67 ground deformation to be predicted with high accuracy [15]. These methods
68 have been instrumental in capturing the nonlinear and spatially variable
69 nature of ground behaviour in post-mining scenarios.

70 In recent years, satellite-based remote sensing technologies, and particu-
71 larly Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSInSAR) [16] and Interferometric
72 Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) [17], have gained prominence as powerful
73 tools for tracking surface displacement over extensive areas. Generally such

74 datasets not only support the validation of simulation models but also enable
75 early detection of active subsidence zones.

76 The role of pillar mechanics remains central to subsidence analysis [10],
77 with hydrogeological factors introducing additional layers of complexity. Vari-
78 ations in groundwater regimes due to aquifer drawdown [14] or mine inunda-
79 tion [18] can significantly modify pore pressure distributions and weaken the
80 mechanical properties of the rock mass, thereby influencing deformation pat-
81 terns at the surface [15]. One limitation of the current state of the art is the
82 lack of data from seismic monitoring of R&P mining (without depillaring)
83 and comparisons between the recorded seismicity and surface subsidence.

84 The objective of the present study is to evaluate the complex seismic-
85 ity registered during R&P trial testing at great depth in comparison to the
86 subsidence observed at the surface. Schreiber et al. [3] presented some first
87 results from induced seismicity monitoring of the first panel of a R&P trial
88 in the USCB. For this reason, the results of seismic monitoring of the first
89 panel [3] were extended, and were analysed in detail together with unpub-
90 lished results from the second panel. The use of seismoacoustic monitoring
91 in areas at high risk of rockburst during longwall mining was tested during
92 the R&P trial as a possible technique for rock masses at risk of rockburst.
93 A comparison of the registered seismicity with the measured subsidence at
94 the surface is presented here to give a complex view of R&P mining at great
95 depth. The results represent a unique study of the induced seismicity and
96 surface subsidence associated with R&P without depillaring.

97 **2. Site conditions**

98 A study of induced seismicity and surface deformations was conducted
99 during the development of Panels 1 and 2 in coal seam No. 30 at the CSM
100 mine (Fig. 1). These panels were located within the shaft protective pillar
101 at depths ranging from 700 to 900 m. In Panel 1, the coal seam was 4.1
102 m thick, including an inter-burden parting of 0.5 m thick siltstone, while in
103 Panel 2, the seam was 3.5 m thick, including a 0.5 m thick siltstone band.
104 The average dip of the seam was approximately 12° , with the inclination
105 occasionally approaching 20° . All roadways were developed with a bolter
106 miner with a 1.5–2.5 m cut-out distance, followed by the installation of high-
107 capacity, pretensioned, resin-grouted rock bolts in the roof and pillar rib sides
108 [19]. Rhomboid pillars with an acute corner angle of 70° were developed by
109 driving rectangular roadways of 3.5–4.5 m in height and 5.2 m in width. In

Figure 1: Geological and mining conditions in the area of the R&P testing site, with the positions of the seismic stations.

110 Panel 1, staggered development was carried out to avoid three- and four-way
 111 junctions with rhomboid pillar sizes in the range 16×26 m – 30×35 m, while
 112 in Panel 2, both four- and five-way junctions were developed. The pillar sizes
 113 for Panel 2 varied in the range 20×25 m – 24×83 m. It was anticipated that
 114 the presence of slippery slickenside beds in the roof and floor would reduce
 115 the lateral stress confinement within the coal pillars, which would further
 116 decrease the pillar strength [20].

117 The roof rocks consist of alternating layers of sandstone and siltstone.
 118 From the bottom to the top, the roof rocks are composed as follows. On
 119 top of coal seam No. 30 is a thick layer of siltstone, with small layers of

Figure 2: Typical lithological structure of the rock mass in the area under study [3].

120 grained sandstones. The thickness varies in this area from 18 to 24 m. The
 121 formation continues with fine-grained and coarse-grained sandstone layers
 122 with thicknesses of 9–14 m, and finally a layer of siltstone 2–13 m thick,
 123 which represents the nearest sub-layer of coal seam No. 29. Underneath
 124 seam No. 29, a small unmarked seam of 1–9 m in depth and 0.7–1.2 m in
 125 thickness is locally present.

126 The bedrocks of seam No. 30 are formed, from the top to the bottom, of
 127 a layer of siltstone 0.6–1.4 m thick, underneath which is coal seam No. 31,
 128 with a thickness of 0.6–1.0 m. The formation continues with a 4–8 m layer of
 129 siltstone, underneath which is coal seam No. 32. All three coal seams (Nos.
 130 30, 31 and 32) become closer towards the west, and a complex coal mass of
 131 almost 6 m in thickness is formed. Under seam No. 32 is root siltstone of
 132 thickness 1–7 m. All stratigraphical units are shown in Fig. 2 .

133 Stratigraphical studies of the area proved the existence of thrust faults
 134 (see Fig. 1) near the mining area, which was confirmed by roadway driving
 135 in coal seam No. 30. The amplitude of the faults ranged from 1 to 5 m.
 136 The fault line lies to the northwest, cleaving 1 small overlaps further to the
 137 north, and is relatively horizontal, at an angle of 20°. A few small overlap
 138 structures were expected to be present at the final stage of the mining in the

Table 1: Uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) of rocks

Rock type	Average UCS [MPa]
Sandstone	123.8
Siltstone	90.3
Root siltstone	63.3
Coal seam	21.9

139 first mining site, but their existence was negligible in regard to the mining
 140 process. Other mining and geological structures can be seen in the site map
 141 in Fig. 1, with the location of the R&P panels.

142 In geomechanical terms, the area has been studied in the past via several
 143 geological drillings. The cores were examined and geomechanically evaluated,
 144 and the results provided an understanding of the strength properties of the
 145 rocks, including information about lumpiness and the number and angle of
 146 the discontinuities in the core of the drilling [21]. All of these factors can
 147 affect the final calculation of the distribution of the pillars and their stability
 148 properties. The median values of the calculated compressive strength of rocks
 149 can be seen in Table 1.

150 3. Microseismic monitoring

151 3.1. Seismological observations

152 As the first part of seismological observations, we used a Seismological
 153 Polygon Monitoring System (SP, see Fig. 3). This regional network consists
 154 of 10 triaxial short-period WDS seismometers ($f = 0\text{--}2.0$ Hz), 6 of which
 155 are located in boreholes (depth 30 m), three are installed underground in
 156 active mines, and one is situated in a short gallery at the Ostrava-Krasne
 157 Pole seismic station. The frequency range of the network is 2–32 Hz, and
 158 the dynamics of the recorded seismic signals around 120 dB, with sampling
 159 frequency 125 Hz [3]. The positions of these stations were distributed around
 160 active and inactive mines to provide a continuous data stream illustrating the
 161 changing seismological activity over time. The purposes of these stations are
 162 to provide nominal basic data and to enable evaluation of the seismological
 163 activity in the whole region of the southern part of the USCB.

164 As the second part of seismological observations, data from the local seis-
 165 mological networks (see Fig. 3) of active mines were used. The stations
 166 comprising this networks are situated in the local mines, and are equipped

Figure 3: Seismological networks.

167 with monoaxial, low-frequency and low-periodical vertical SM-3 seismome-
 168 ters. The basic parameters of these seismometers are as follows: input sen-
 169 sitivity 16–5 mV, amplification maximum 74 dB, frequency range 1.5–20 Hz,
 170 and sampling frequency 100 Hz.

171 A micro-seismological monitoring system was designed in the area of the
 172 R&P testing site. For the purpose of more accurate localisation of the events,
 173 the original local seismic network of the CSM mine was extended by about
 174 6 seismic stations surrounding the actual R&P mining area (see Fig. 1).
 175 In the final stage, the network consisted of 11 stations equipped with axial,
 176 low-frequency and low-periodical vertical seismographs (as described in the
 177 previous paragraph).

178 The data were stored in a single database. Seismological data from re-
 179 gional and local networks were evaluated together, using software that was
 180 originally custom-made.

181 3.2. Seismoacoustic observations

182 Seismoacoustic monitoring is used commonly in longwall mines in areas
 183 with a high risk of rockburst. The registration base is composed of five
 184 geophones, which monitor elastic vibrations in the frequency range 40 Hz

185 to 2 kHz. Four geophones (SAC-1B) are located in the coal seam, and one
186 (SAC-1A) is located in the roof rocks (see Fig. 4). Geophones are fixed
187 into the rock mass via a mechanical wedge at a depth of approx. 4 m,
188 and allow for the 3D location of seismic events. Underground structured
189 cabling with geophones creates an underground structure for the monitoring
190 system. The UGA-SA evaluation apparatus is located on the surface, and
191 enables continual evaluation of registered events. The evaluation of spatial
192 and temporal seismoacoustic events is necessary for:

- 193 • determination of criteria for the normal and anomalous development of
194 seismoacoustic activity,
- 195 • operational implementation of active and passive rockburst measures,
- 196 • evaluation of the effectiveness of active and passive rockburst measures
197 (mainly in coal seams),
- 198 • possible extensions of waiting time after destress blasting,
- 199 • removal of miners from underground openings in the case of unfavourable
200 development of seismoacoustic activity.

201 The main goal of testing this method was to verify its usability during
202 R&P mining. Many modifications to the locations of geophones were tested
203 according to the driving of new corridors and the locations of old corridors.

204 **4. Surface monitoring**

205 Following the regulations of the Regional Mining Authority, vertical dis-
206 placements are measured to document surface movements as an effect of
207 mining. These measurements are carried out using the technical levelling
208 method, with centimetre accuracy, twice a year during the entire mining pe-
209 riod and over the next five years. The purpose of these measurements is
210 related to the density of the measured points and their location in the area
211 under influence. Although this frequency of measurements enables the as-
212 sessment of mine damage, it is insufficient from the point of view of research
213 into the development of the subsidence trough. Another question relates
214 to the quality of the measured data with regard to statistical proof of the
215 expected values of surface subsidence. When there is evidence of surface
216 subsidence due to longwall mining and the total surface subsidence reaches

Figure 4: Positions of seismoacoustic monitoring equipment in longwalls with a high risk of rockburst [22, 23].

217 several metres, a measurement accuracy on the order of centimetres is suf-
 218 ficient. For example, in the area between the CSM North and South mine
 219 sites, the terrain has subsided by about 14 m. From the point of view of the
 220 rules for assessing mine damage, the affected area is defined by an isoline of
 221 subsidence of 4 cm (a value determined by the Regional Mining Authority
 222 for the territory of the Czech part of the Upper Silesian basin). However, for
 223 research into the effects of mining on the surface due to the R&P method, it
 224 was necessary to design and implement a targeted monitoring scheme that
 225 could provide results with millimetre accuracy for both position and height.

226 In general, there are several methods for monitoring surface movements.
 227 Among the most widely used is the GNSS method, which makes it possible
 228 to determine the position and height of a monitored point with millimetre
 229 accuracy during long-term linear movements of the ground surface, based
 230 on data measured in continuous mode [24, 25]. However, in the area of a
 231 mine, it is difficult to stabilise the GNSS receiver sufficiently for continuous
 232 monitoring to meet the mine safety rules. Another method is the increas-
 233 ingly popular Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) technology,
 234 which enables the determination of vertical displacements with high accuracy

235 and is used in this regard mainly to analyse the effect of deep mining on the
236 ground surface [26]. Using this method, we monitored the dynamic formation
237 of the subsidence trough in the Karvina sub-basin [27, 28, 29], and clarified
238 the cause of short-term surface uplifts during longwall mining near the shaft
239 protective pillar [30] where the R&P mining method was carried out on a
240 trial basis between May 2014 and October 2017.

241 The task of the trial was not only to prove the applicability of the R&P
242 method in the Ostrava–Karvina Coalfield (OKC) conditions, but also to as-
243 sess the intensity of the effects of undermining on the surface; a proper mon-
244 itoring system for the surface was therefore proposed. Stabilisation of the
245 control points on the surface took place even before the start of mining us-
246 ing the R&P method. Measurement of the heights of the control points was
247 carried out by precise levelling, and at each stage, the measurement heights
248 were made with reference to the unmined area. The first measurement was
249 carried out on February 4, 2014 (one month before the start of testing), and
250 measurements were subsequently carried out three times per year. A total of
251 21 measurement stages were carried out, with the last taking place on June
252 10, 2020.

253 **5. Methodology for data evaluation**

254 *5.1. Automated spatiotemporal evaluation of mining-induced seismicity*

255 In the context of assessing seismic risks associated with underground min-
256 ing, a dedicated software framework has been developed that integrates the
257 computational capabilities of Microsoft Excel with the three-dimensional vi-
258 sualisation functions of Voxler software (Golden Software). This custom-built
259 tool facilitates the automated spatiotemporal analysis and graphical inter-
260 pretation of seismic phenomena in relation to the progression of underground
261 mining operations, with specific applicability to longwall and R&P mining
262 methods.

263 The fundamental component of the framework under discussion is a macro
264 developed in Visual Basic for Applications (VBA). The purpose of this macro
265 is to ensure dynamic synchronisation between data processing in Microsoft
266 Excel and 3D visualisation in Voxler software. A key feature of the system
267 is the temporal control window, which enables users to specify a target date
268 and an associated analytical time range, extending for a number of days
269 prior to and following a designated date. Once the temporal parameters have
270 been established, the tool generates a series of graphical outputs, including a

271 detailed 3D map illustrating the extent of the areas that have been mined to
272 date, as well as the spatial distribution of seismic events occurring within the
273 specified temporal window. The seismic events are visualised using variable
274 symbology that reflects their associated energy levels by size and colour.
275 Earlier seismic events falling outside the primary temporal window may also
276 be optionally displayed using a subdued visual style, to provide contextual
277 insight into ongoing seismic trends. Concurrently, a synchronised graph is
278 generated in Microsoft Excel to depict the relationship between seismic load
279 (or seismic activity) and the advancement of mining operations.

280 This dual-output approach enables the visual and analytical correlation
281 of seismicity with mining progress. Summary charts and 3D maps of seismic
282 event distributions are automatically compiled for each scenario, and can be
283 easily exported as image files to facilitate reporting and communication. The
284 interpretation of daily and weekly seismic energy summary outputs allows
285 for the timely identification of anomalous or spatially heterogeneous seismic
286 patterns, which may be indicative of geomechanical changes within the rock
287 mass.

288 The methodology presented here provides a practical analytical tool for
289 correlating mining activities with induced seismic responses, thereby support-
290 ing both operational planning and strategic risk assessment. This approach
291 represents a significant methodological advancement in the field of automated
292 seismic interpretation within underground mining. The effectiveness of the
293 tool is validated by application to real-world R&P datasets, and a demon-
294 stration of its capability to evaluate the spatial and temporal evolution of
295 seismicity in relation to daily mining progression is presented later in this
296 article.

297 *5.2. Induced seismicity*

298 In order to evaluate the collected seismic (seismological and seismoacous-
299 tic) activity data, the following techniques were used:

- 300 • location maps of seismic events registered during the driving of road-
301 ways,
- 302 • graphs of the total seismic energy registered on a daily and weekly.

303 From these maps and graphs, the accumulation of registered events can be
304 identified and the most significant weekly energy variations can be obtained
305 for a given geological, geomechanical and mining situation.

Figure 5: Locations of R&P panels and control points.

306 *5.3. Subsidence*

307 In order to investigate the effects of R&P mining on the surface, height
 308 measurements were taken at eight control points located above the protective
 309 pillar of the CSM North shaft. Their positions in relation to the R&P mining
 310 process are shown in Fig. 5.

311 The heights of the control points were measured by precise levelling, and
 312 each measurement was made with reference to the height-stable point GZ10-
 313 64.2 located in an unmined area. Measurements were made with a Leica DNA
 314 03 electronic levelling instrument, with 3-m-long invar battens. The standard
 315 deviation of this instrument, as stated by the manufacturer, is 0.3 mm. The

316 levelling line was measured twice in each case (forward and backward), and
317 the deviation determined from this double measurement was compared with
318 the permitted deviation for precise levelling measurements obtained from Eq.
319 1:

$$\Delta = \pm 5\sqrt[3]{L^2} \quad (1)$$

320 where:

321 Δ – permitted deviation between two measurements of the elevation of
322 the levelling line [mm],

323 L – length of the levelling line [km].

324 The accuracy of the levelling measurements was also calculated based on
325 the mean kilometre error, which is used for open levelling lines, where the
326 levelling line starts at a point with a known height and ends at a point whose
327 height is determined. The average kilometre error characterises the accuracy
328 of the height of any point along the levelling line, which in this case ranged
329 from 0.6 to 1.6 mm. It was determined using Eq. 2:

$$m_0 = \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_R} \left[\frac{dd}{s} \right]} \quad (2)$$

330 where:

331 n_R – number of levelling units,

332 d – difference in the height elevation of the levelling unit determined from
333 a double measurement (forward and backward) [mm],

334 s – length of the levelling unit [km].

335 Vertical displacements were calculated based on the differences in heights
336 of the levelling points determined in the individual measurement stages. The
337 vertical displacements along the line of control points Nos. 1 to 8 are shown
338 in Fig. 6. The first levelling measurement took place on 02/04/2014, and the
339 results provided the height values against which the vertical displacements
340 from all subsequent levelling measurements were determined. The vertical
341 movements that occurred on 26/10/2017 (i.e. immediately after the end of
342 mining) and the total vertical movements determined for the last levelling
343 measurement, carried out on 06/10/2020, are shown in Table 2. A negative
344 value for the vertical displacement represents surface subsidence.

345 The accuracy of the vertical displacement measurements of the control
346 points ranges from 0.9 to 2.3 mm, depending on the accuracy of determining
347 the height of the points at the beginning and end of the time period (i.e.

Table 2: Vertical movement of control points Nos. 1–8 [mm].

Control point No.	From 02/04/2014		From 26/10/2017
	to 26/10/2017	to 06/10/2020	to 06/10/2020
1	-71.2	-182.3	-111.1
2	-76.4	-194.9	-118.5
3	-85.4	-209.3	-123.9
4	-92.9	-223.6	-130.7
5	-100.6	-240.5	-139.9
6	-103.5	-257.9	-154.4
7	-107.6	-284.4	-176.8
8	-128.0	-337.8	-209.8

348 the specific value of the mean error of levelling). Subsidence determined by
 349 values exceeding the confidence interval are designated as proven with the
 350 appropriate risk. A confidence interval with a risk of 5 % was determined as
 351 twice the mean error of the vertical displacements.

352 When assessing the effects of R&P mining on the surface, the measured
 353 heights of the control point RN 146.1 in the area of the CSM Mine, which
 354 is stabilised based on the masonry of the building, were also used (Fig. 5).
 355 The first height measurement at this point was carried out in 1959, and
 356 measurements have since been made once a year using the precise levelling
 357 method. The total subsidence of control point RN 146.1, i.e. from the first
 358 levelling measurement to the measurement carried out in 2017 (at the end of
 359 the trial of the R&P method), is 937 mm (Fig. 7). Control point RN 146.1
 360 is connected by levelling measurement to point GZ-10.64.2, which is located
 361 outside the area affected by undermining, i.e. to the same starting point as
 362 in the case of the eight control points along the levelling line. The measured
 363 heights of the control point RN 146.1 over the entire measurement period are
 364 shown in the graph in Fig. 7, together with the annual subsidence over the
 365 years 2013–2017.

366 During excavation of the R&P panels, measurements of the roadway roof
 367 subsidence were carried out successively for both Panels 1 and 2. Subsidence
 368 was evaluated based on the results of trigonometric levelling carried out by
 369 workers of the mining company. The levelling line ran from the height point
 370 stabilised in the fourth level near to the shaft, through the points of the

Figure 6: Vertical displacements along the line of control points 1 to 8 for the entire monitored period, with reference to the first measurement carried out on 04/02/2014.

371 polygonal line, up to the monitored points that had been stabilised in the
 372 roofs of Panels 1 and 2. Work on Panel 1 was started in 05/2014, and
 373 terminated in 09/2015. During its closure, access to part of the Panel 1 was
 374 maintained so that the stabilised control points 11 to 20 (shown in Fig. 5)
 375 could be further monitored. Subsequently, work on Panel 2 took place until
 376 10/2017, during which height control points 21 to 28 (Fig. 5) were measured
 377 over the entire period of accessibility of Panel 2, i.e. from 11/2015 to 09/2017.
 378 The roadway roof subsidence at control points 11 to 28, over the total period
 379 of measurement by trigonometric levelling, is shown in Tables 3 and 4. The
 380 largest subsidence, with values exceeding 300 mm, was observed at control
 381 points 18 and 27, i.e. in the location of the tectonic zone (Fig. 5). Control
 382 point 28 also subsided by 0.117 m in seven months. Control points 16 and 17
 383 were monitored over the longest period. Based on the measurement results
 384 for Panels 1 and 2, and taking into account the tectonic conditions of the
 385 given location and the total period of monitoring, a roadway roof subsidence
 386 value of 250 mm was assumed for the subsequent calculations of the effect of
 387 the R&P method on the surface.

Table 3: Roadway roof subsidence of R&P Panel 1 over the given time period [m].

Point	Subsidence	Time period
11	-0.183	01/2015–02/2016
12	-0.241	12/2014–03/2017
13	-0.255	03/2015–03/2017
14	-0.220	02/2015–02/2016
15	-0.232	01/2015–03/2017
16	-0.279	11/2014–03/2017
17	-0.235	11/2014–03/2017
18	-0.371	11/2014–02/2016
19	-0.220	08/2014–02/2016
20	-0.049	10/2015–03/2017

Table 4: Roadway roof subsidence of R&P Panel 2 over the given time period [m].

Point	Subsidence	Time period
21	-0.148	11/2015–09/2017
22	-0.215	11/2015–09/2017
23	-0.131	12/2015–09/2017
24	-0.191	02/2016–09/2017
25	-0.214	08/2016–09/2017
26	-0.282	09/2016–09/2017
27	-0.329	11/2016–09/2017
28	-0.117	02/2017–09/2017

Figure 7: Elevations of control point RN 146.1 from 1959 to 2017. The point is situated in the area of the CSM North mine.

388 6. Results and discussion

389 6.1. Seismological observations

390 A graph showing the total daily registered seismic energy and the weekly
 391 slope of the registered seismic energy during the driving of the Panels 1
 392 and 2 is presented in Fig. 8. The registered seismic activity is low because
 393 it is related solely to the driving of roadways. Daily registered seismicity
 394 varied around $20 \sqrt{J}$ per day, increasing to above $60 \sqrt{J}$ and reaching an
 395 extreme of $182.1 \sqrt{J}$ per day in some specific conditions. The weekly slope
 396 of the registered seismic energy varied between 10 and $20 \sqrt{J}$ per day during
 397 driving of the Panel 1, fluctuated around $20 \sqrt{J}$ per day during the driving
 398 of corridors between Panels 1 and 2, and was approximately $30 \sqrt{J}$ per day
 399 during work on the second Panel 2 (see Fig. 8). Despite the generally low
 400 registered seismicity, three phases could be identified based on the level of
 401 seismic activity: (i) during driving of the Panel 1, (ii) during driving of
 402 roadways between Panels 1 and 2, and (iii) during driving of the Panel 2 (see
 403 Fig. 8). The level of selection of registered anomalies was chosen separately
 404 for each phase based on the overall level of registered seismicity in each phase
 405 ($30 \sqrt{J}$ per day for the first phase, $20 \sqrt{J}$ per day for the second phase, and
 406 $40 \sqrt{J}$ per day for the third phase; see Fig. 8). The selected periods were
 407 analysed in detail.

408 A detailed analysis of the selected periods of seismic observations during

Figure 8: Registered seismicity for the R&P Panel 1 (cases involving an increase in seismic activity selected for detailed analysis shown as green circles; cases selected for presentation marked as numbers in green circles).

409 the driving of R&P roadways enabled the identification of two geomechanical
 410 situations involving increased seismic activity: during the driving of road-
 411 ways, and approaching to already driven roadways of R&P panel (creation
 412 of diamond shape pillars) or to old roadways driven in the past.

413 All of the selected cases involving increases in seismic activity presented
 414 in Fig. 8 represent situations when a roadway is driven in the direction
 415 of an existing R&P roadway or an old roadway driven in the past. The
 416 first example (marked as 1 in Fig. 8) considered for a detailed analysis of
 417 the registered seismicity and roadway advances in this type of situation is
 418 illustrated in Fig. 9.

419 Fig. 9 shows the daily registered seismicity and the daily roadway advance
 420 (represented by the red arrow in the image for 25/11/2014). The roadway
 421 advance at the end of the first day is shown in Fig. 9 as well as the registered
 422 seismicity during the day. During the first day (25/11/2014), when the daily
 423 roadway advance was 8 m, five seismic events with energy 10^1 J and one
 424 with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area (where the distance to the
 425 previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 31 m).
 426 During the second day (26/11/2014), when the daily roadway advance was
 427 10 m, 25 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and seven with energy 10^2 J

Figure 9: Registered seismicity and roadway driving advances in R&P Panel 1 over the period 24/11/2014 to 30/11/2014.

428 were registered, as marked in Fig. 9 (where the distance to the previously
 429 driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 21 m). During
 430 the third day (27/11/2014), when the daily roadway advance was 8 m, 21
 431 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and 10 with energy 10^2 J were registered
 432 (where the distance to the previously driven roadway in the forefield at the
 433 end of the day was 13 m). On the fourth day (28/11/2014), when the daily
 434 roadway advance was 6 m, 25 seismic events of energy 10^1 J and five with
 435 energy 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the previously driven
 436 roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 7 m). On the fifth day
 437 (29/11/2014), when the daily roadway advance was 7 m, 18 seismic events
 438 with energy 10^1 J and two with energy 10^2 J were registered (where the
 439 driven roadway was connected to the roadway in the forefield at the end of

Figure 10: Registered seismicity and roadway driving advances in R&P Panel 1 over the period 15/06/2015 to 19/06/2015.

440 the day). During the sixth day (30/11/2014), when no roadway was driven,
 441 only eight seismic events with energy 10^1 J were registered in the area. The
 442 seismic events registered during the approach of the roadway to the previously
 443 driven roadway were registered mainly in the area of the pillar where the
 444 driven roadway was created (in the right rib of the driven roadway), and in
 445 the area of the created pillar (in the left rib of the driven roadway). During
 446 the approach of the roadway to the previously driven roadway, the number
 447 of seismic events increased in general, and mainly included events of higher
 448 energy (10^2 J), primarily at a distance of the roadway face of about 13 m
 449 from the old roadway.

450 The second example (marked as 2 in Fig. 8) considered for a detailed
 451 analysis of the registered seismicity and roadway advances is shown in Fig.
 452 10, and involved roadways in the second half of the Panel 1 driven over the
 453 period 15/06/2015 to 19/06/2015.

454 Fig. 10 shows the daily registered seismicity and the daily roadway ad-
 455 vances (represented by the red arrow in the image for 16/06/2015). The
 456 roadway advance at the end of each day is shown in the figure, as well as
 457 the seismicity registered during the day. During the first day in this pe-
 458 riod (15/06/2015), which did not include roadway driving, no seismic events

459 were recorded (this day is not displayed in Fig. 10). On the second day
460 (16/06/2015), when the daily roadway advance was 6 m, 11 seismic events
461 with energy 10^1 J and one with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area
462 (where the distance to the previous driven roadway in the forefield at the
463 end of the day was 24 m). During the third day (17/06/2015), when the
464 daily roadway advance was 11 m, 53 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and
465 two with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area (where the distance to the
466 previous driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 13 m).
467 During the fourth day (18/06/2015), when the daily roadway advance was
468 13 m, 26 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and three with energy 10^2 J were
469 registered in the area (where the driven roadway was connected to the road-
470 way in the forefield at the end of the day). On the fifth day (19/06/2015),
471 when the daily roadway advance was 16 m, 13 seismic events with energy 10^1
472 J and two with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area. Roadway driving
473 continued in a straight line on this day. During the approach of the roadway
474 to the previously driven roadway, the number of seismic events increased in
475 general and included events of higher energy (10^2 J), mainly at a distance
476 of the roadway face of about 13 m from the old roadway. The increased
477 seismicity is mainly located in the area of the pillars created on the right and
478 left sides of the rib of the driven roadway.

479 Fig. 11 shows the third example (marked as 3 in Fig. 8) considered for
480 a detailed analysis of the registered seismicity and roadway advance. In this
481 case, the roadway at the start of the Panel 2 was driven over the period from
482 29/02/2016 to 05/03/2016.

483 The daily registered seismicity and the daily roadway advance (shown by
484 the red arrow in the image for 29/02/2016) are shown in Fig. 11. On the
485 first day under study (29/02/2016), which did not involve roadway driving,
486 three seismic events with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area. During
487 the second day (01/03/2016), when the daily roadway advance was 7 m, one
488 seismic event with energy 10^1 J and four with energy 10^2 J were registered in
489 the area (where the distance to the previous driven roadway in the forefield
490 at the end of the day was 26 m). On the third day (02/03/2016), when the
491 daily roadway advance was 8 m, four seismic events with energy 10^1 J and
492 eight with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area (where the distance to the
493 previous driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 18 m).

494 On the fourth day (03/03/2016), when the daily roadway advance was
495 9 m, eight seismic events with energy 10^1 J and 20 with energy 10^2 J were
496 registered in the area (when the distance to the previously driven roadway in

Figure 11: Registered seismicity and roadway driving advances in R&P Panel 2 over the period 29/02/2016 to 05/03/2016.

497 the forefield at the end of the day was 9 m). On the fifth day (04/03/2016),
 498 when the daily roadway advance was 9 m, 10 seismic events with energy
 499 10^1 J and eight with energy 10^2 J were registered in the area (the driven
 500 roadway was connected to the roadway in the fore filed at the end of the
 501 day). During the sixth day (05/03/2016), when no roadway was driven (and
 502 only an adjustment to the roadway connection to the old roadway was carried
 503 out), seven seismic events with energy 10^1 J and four with energy 10^2 J were
 504 registered in the area.

505 During the approach of the roadway to the previously driven roadway,
 506 the number of seismic events increased in general, and most were of higher
 507 energy (10^2 J), primarily at a distance of the roadway face of about 18 m

Figure 12: Registered seismicity and roadway driving advances in R&P Panel 2 over the period 17/02/2017 to 24/02/2017.

508 from the old roadway. The increased seismicity was mainly located in the
 509 area of the pillars created on the right and left sides of the rib of the driven
 510 roadway.

511 Fig. 12 shows the fourth example (marked as 4 in Fig. 8) considered for
 512 a detailed analysis of the registered seismicity and roadway advance. The
 513 roadway in the second half of Panel 2 was driven over the period 17/02/2017
 514 to 24/02/2017.

515 The daily registered seismicity and the daily roadway advance (marked by
 516 the red arrow in the image for 17/02/2017) are shown in Fig. 12. During the
 517 first investigated day (17/02/2017), when the daily roadway advance was 6 m,

518 12 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and one with energy 10^2 J were registered
519 in the area (where the distance to the previously driven roadway in the
520 forefield at the end of the day was 30 m). On the second day (18/02/2017),
521 when the daily roadway advance was 5 m, 17 seismic events with energy 10^1
522 J and three with energy 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the
523 previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 25 m).
524 On the third day (19/02/2017), on which there was no roadway advance, 19
525 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and five with energy 10^2 J were registered
526 (where the distance to the previously driven roadway in the forefield at the
527 end of the day was 25 m). On the fourth day (20/02/2017), when the roadway
528 advance was 9 m, 25 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and one with energy
529 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the previously driven roadway in
530 the forefield at the end of the day was 16 m). On the fifth day (21/02/2017),
531 when the daily roadway advance was 13 m, 26 seismic events with energy
532 10^1 J and three with energy 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the
533 previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 3 m). On
534 the sixth day (22/02/2017), when the daily roadway advance was 12 m (3 m
535 to the first old roadway and 9 m as a continuation of the next roadway in
536 the same direction), 19 seismic events with energy 10^1 J and one with energy
537 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the previously driven roadway
538 in the forefield at the end of the day was 20 m). During the seventh day
539 (23/02/2017), when the daily roadway advance was 10 m, 22 seismic events
540 with energy 10^1 J and three with energy 10^2 J were registered (where the
541 distance to the previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the
542 day was 10 m). During the eighth day (24/02/2017), when the daily roadway
543 advance was 10 m, 25 seismic events with energy 10^1 J were registered (where
544 the driven roadway was connected to the roadway in the forefield at the end
545 of the day). During the approach of the roadway to the previously driven
546 roadway (in both cases), the number of seismic events increased in general,
547 and most were of energy (10^1 J), primarily at distances of the roadway face
548 of about 16 and 10 m, respectively, from the old roadways. The increased
549 seismicity was mainly located in the area of the pillars created on the left
550 side of the rib of the driven roadway and in the area surrounding the driven
551 roadway.

552 Increases in recorded seismicity have also been recorded during roadway
553 driving near tectonic faults, as this process activates the fracturing of rock
554 masses in the vicinity of tectonic faults. These cases are shown in Fig. 13.

555 The first case involved seismic activity during roadway driving in the first

Figure 13: Registered seismicity for (A) the first part of R&P Panel 1, and (B) the second part of R&P Panel 2.

556 part of Panel 1 (see Fig. 13a). The driving of roadways near the tectonic
 557 fault (overthrust to the south of the roadway) caused the activation of rock
 558 mass fracturing over a wide area of the roadway, mainly in the area of the
 559 overthrust, where numerous seismic events of energy 10^1 and 10^2 J were
 560 recorded. The second case involved seismic activity during roadway driving
 561 in the last part of Panel 2 (see Fig. 13b). The driving of roadways near
 562 the tectonic faults activated fracturing of the rock mass over a wide area (in
 563 the region where the tectonic faults crossed the R&P panel). Many seismic
 564 events were recorded in the area surrounding the R&P, rather than solely in
 565 the area of the created pillars, with energy levels of 10^1 and 10^2 J. In addition,
 566 during the driving of roadways at the end of the R&P panel, as the roadways
 567 approached the tectonic fault, numerous seismic events with energy levels
 568 of 10^1 and 10^2 J were recorded near the tectonic fault. In general, roadway
 569 driving for the Panel 2 provoked many seismic events outside the area of the
 570 R&P panel, along the tectonic faults running from the south and south-east
 571 towards the R&P panel.

572 *6.2. Seismoacoustic observations*

573 Seismoacoustic observations of the coal seam were carried out with geo-
574 phones at different locations, using old roadways driven in the past. How-
575 ever, in many cases, the observation base (location of geophones) could not
576 be achieved in a way that was ideal for the monitoring of seismoacoustic
577 activity inside the location base. Anomalies recorded during these seismoa-
578 coustic observations were identified in similar time and location as anomalies
579 of seismic activity. Examples are presented following the periods discussed in
580 previous chapter 6.1, but only in limited numbers. The first example selected
581 for a detailed analysis involved the registered seismoacoustic activity associ-
582 ated with the roadway advances shown in Fig. 14, when the roadway for the
583 second half Panel 1 was driven in the period from 25/11/2014 to 30/11/2014.

584 The daily registered seismoacoustic activity and the daily roadway ad-
585 vances (red arrow in 25/11/2014) are shown in Fig. 14. During the first day
586 (25/11/2014), when the daily roadway advance was 8 m, one seismoacoustic
587 event with energy 10^0 J and 12 with energy 10^1 J were registered in the area
588 (where the distance to the previously driven roadway in the forefield at the
589 end of the day was 31 m). On the second day (26/11/2014), when the daily
590 roadway advance was 10 m, seven seismoacoustic events with energy 10^0 J,
591 eight with energy 10^1 J and one with energy 10^2 J were registered (where
592 the distance to previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the
593 day was 21 m). During the third day (27/11/2014), when the daily roadway
594 advance was 8 m, 10 seismoacoustic events with energy 10^0 J, 19 with energy
595 10^1 J and two with energy 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the
596 previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 13 m).
597 On the fourth day (28/11/2014), when the daily roadway advance was 6 m,
598 two seismoacoustic events with energy 10^0 J, 18 with energy 10^1 J and three
599 seismic events with energy 10^2 J were registered (where the distance to the
600 previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was 7 m). On
601 the fifth day (29/11/2014), when the daily roadway advance was 7 m, four
602 seismoacoustic events with energy 10^0 J and 18 seismic events with energy
603 10^1 J were registered (where the driven roadway was connected to the road-
604 way in the forefield at the end of the day). On the sixth day (30/11/2014),
605 when no roadway was driven, four seismoacoustic events with energy 10^0 J
606 and six with energy 10^1 J were registered. The seismic events registered as
607 the roadway approached the previously driven roadway occurred mainly in
608 the area of the pillar as the driven roadway was created, with a small number
609 of events in the area of the created pillars and a few outside this area. During

Figure 14: Registered seismoacoustic activity in the coal seam and roadway driving advances in R&P Panel 1 over the period 25/11/2014 to 30/11/2014.

610 the approach of the roadway to the previously driven roadway, the number
 611 of seismoacoustic events increased in general, with an energy level mainly
 612 about 10^1 J, and primarily at a distance between the roadway face location
 613 and the old roadway of about 13 m.

614 The second example chosen for a detailed analysis involved the registered
 615 seismoacoustic activity and roadway advances for the type of situation shown
 616 in Fig. 15, where the roadway for the second half of the Panel 1 was driven
 617 in the period from 15/06/2015 to 19/06/2015.

618 Fig. 15 shows the daily registered seismoacoustic activity and the daily
 619 roadway advances (indicated by the red arrow in the image for 16/06/2015).

Figure 15: Registered SA activity in coal seam and roadway driving advances in R&P Panel 1 over the period 15/06/2015 to 19/06/2015.

620 On the first day (15/06/2015), on which there was no roadway driving, no
 621 seismoacoustic events were recorded (this day is not displayed in Fig. 15).
 622 On the second day (16/06/2015), when the daily roadway advance was 6 m,
 623 two seismoacoustic events with energy 10^0 J and eight with energy 10^1 J were
 624 registered in the area (where the distance to the previously driven roadway in
 625 the forefield at the end of the day was 24 m). On the third day (17/06/2015),
 626 when the daily roadway advance was 11 m, one seismoacoustic event with
 627 energy 10^0 J and 21 with energy 10^1 J were registered (where the distance
 628 to the previously driven roadway in the forefield at the end of the day was
 629 13 m). On the fourth day (18/06/2015), when the daily roadway advance
 630 was 13 m, three events with energy 10^1 J were registered (where the driven
 631 roadway was connected to the roadway in the forefield at the end of the
 632 day). On the fifth day (19/06/2015), when the daily roadway advance was
 633 16 m, five seismoacoustic events with energy 10^1 J were registered. Roadway
 634 driving continued in the same direction on this day. During the approach of
 635 the roadway to the previously driven roadway, the number of seismoacous-
 636 tic events significantly increased, mainly at a distance of the roadway face
 637 location of about 13 m from the old roadway. The increased seismicity was
 638 mainly located in the area of the pillar created on the left side of the rib of
 639 the driven roadway as well as in the area of the pillar created southwards
 640 (where the old roadway in the shape of a hockey stick is located).

641 *6.3. Subsidence*

642 The shaft protective north pillar was not designed as fully protective,
643 but used pillar angles that were steeper compared to the limiting angles of
644 influence. Hence, as a result of mining in the surroundings of the protective
645 pillar, the defined protected area on the surface was also affected. Control
646 points stabilised immediately around the protected area in the area of the
647 CSM Mine (Fig. 5) were therefore affected both by mining using the R&P
648 method and by longwall mining in the surroundings of the CSM North shaft
649 protective pillar. Hence, vertical displacements in the control points do not
650 provide a clear determination of the influence of the R&P mining method on
651 the surface. Our investigation of the effects of R&P mining on the surface
652 had to be based on an analysis of the change in the shape of the coal pillars
653 left in the seam and on effect of these changes on the surface. From the
654 point of view of the effects of mining on the surface, we present a discussion
655 below of the compression of the pillars, the effect on the surface in terms of
656 measured heights, and the theoretical effect of R&P mining on the surface.

657 The reduction in the height of the pillar due to the pressure of the over-
658 lying rocks can be expressed using the deformation parameter $\Delta\varepsilon$, which
659 characterises the compression of the pillar. For the given location, the defor-
660 mation of the pillar due to the pressure of the overburden was determined
661 theoretically as a value of $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.0262$, meaning that a height for the pillar
662 of $g = 4.0$ m would decrease by $\Delta g = 104.8$ mm due to the pressure [31]. *In*
663 *situ* height measurements of individual R&P panels provided information on
664 the roadway roof subsidence between the pillars. The accepted value of 250
665 mm for the roadway roof subsidence indicates that the compression of the
666 pillars probably reached greater values than theoretically assumed.

667 The influence of R&P mining on the surface was analysed based on the
668 vertical displacements of control points Nos. 1 to 8 and the measured results
669 for the heights of control point RN 146.1 in the area of the CSM Mine.
670 The results for the vertical movement of control points Nos.1 to 8 show that
671 between 24/03/2016 and 05/06/2018, a shallow subsidence basin was formed,
672 with the largest subsidence observed first at control point No. 5 and then at
673 point No. 6; following this, the influence of mining in the surroundings of the
674 protective pillar gradually prevailed. The occurrence of this subsidence can
675 be observed from the vertical displacements of the control points shown in
676 Fig. 6. The vertical displacements over the period 04/11/2015 to 05/06/2018
677 are presented in numerical form in Table 4. In both Fig. 6 and Table 5, the
678 values of the vertical displacements are related to the initial measurement,

Table 5: Vertical displacements of control points Nos. 1–8 [mm].

Control point No.	04/11 2015	24/03 2016	02/08 2016	28/10 2016	24/03 2017	08/08 2017	26/10 2017	05/06 2018
1	-18.5	-33.6	-45.7	-46.4	-56.4	-63.4	-71.2	-84.4
2	-21.5	-37.4	-48.5	-49.8	-60.7	-67.8	-76.4	-90.5
3	-23.5	-40.8	-52.7	-54.8	-68.3	-75.3	-85.4	-98.9
4	-24.1	-43.0	-55.1	-58.5	-74.2	-81.8	-92.9	-107.1
5	-25.0	-43.7	-58.5	-63.0	-79.2	-89.0	-100.6	-114.6
6	-24.0	-42.9	-59.1	-64.9	-79.7	-90.6	-103.5	-119.0
7	-23.8	-40.5	-56.9	-65.5	-82.2	-94.4	-107.6	-124.5
8	-28.4	-50.2	-67.6	-78.1	-100.9	-113.9	-128.0	-148.1

679 which took place on 02/04/2014, i.e. before the start of mining using the
680 R&P method.

681 From the measurement results recorded on 24/03/2016, a difference in
682 vertical displacement of 10.1 mm was found between points Nos. 1 and 5.
683 Point No. 8 had already been affected by mining taking place south of the
684 shaft protective pillar. From the following measurement on 02/08/2016, the
685 difference in vertical displacements between points Nos. 1 and 6 was found
686 to be -13.4 mm. This value corresponds to the subsidence of control point
687 RN 146.1, which had been monitored since the beginning of mining in 1968.
688 In 2013 and 2014, this point subsided by 14 and 16 mm/year, respectively.
689 In 2016 and 2017, increases in subsidence were recorded, with values of 33
690 and 32 mm/year, respectively (Fig. 7). It should be noted that this increase
691 in annual subsidence is not caused solely by the influence of R&P mining,
692 but primarily by the mining of longwall panels in the surroundings of the
693 shaft protective pillar.

694 Our assessment of the theoretical effect of the R&P mining method was
695 based on the values of direct measurements of roof subsidence and a veri-
696 fied empirical calculation for its propagation to the surface. If we assume
697 that the roofs of the roadways remained solid, then the compression of the
698 pillars would approximately correspond to the average measured subsidence
699 at the top of the roadways. The accepted value for the roadway roof subsi-
700 dence of 250 mm therefore represents the most probable estimate of the pillar
701 compression. If we assume that the tops of the roadways and pillars have
702 dropped by 250 mm, the theoretical effect of this subsidence on the surface
703 can be calculated using an empirical method based on Knothe [31], which

704 has been used by many authors to assess the effects of mining on the surface
705 [13, 32, 33]. In the Czech part of the USCB, Knothe's method is almost
706 exclusively used for the assessment of mine damage. We applied Knothe's
707 method, with a roadway roof subsidence of 250 mm and an excavation factor
708 of 0.4, to determine by static calculation the subsidence at control point No.
709 6, with a value of 17 mm, and control point RN 146.1, with a value of 11 mm.
710 The value of the mining coefficient was determined on the basis of long-term
711 experience with the solid overburden failure of mined seams in the Karvina
712 sub-basin of the Czech part of the USCB [32].

713 **7. Summary and conclusions**

714 Seismic monitoring as a method for the localisation of low energy tremors
715 has been shown to be an excellent approach that is sufficient for R&P mining
716 without depillaring. Even under potentially unfavourable conditions, such as
717 the presence of tectonic discontinuities, free space between pillars, etc., the
718 system was found to be efficient in identifying anomalies in both seismological
719 and seismoacoustic activity.

720 Detailed analyses of the seismological observations enabled us to identify
721 situations where the activity showed some small anomalies, and these were
722 studied in detail in terms of the natural, mining and geomechanical conditions
723 (Fig. 8). As the new roadways approached previously driven roadways or old
724 mine workings, the activity increased to more than usual; this is most likely
725 to be due to the increased area of fracture around the roadways, especially
726 during the completion of pillars (Figs. 9 to 12). This increase in activity
727 was measured based on the higher number of registered events. Both the
728 increase in the registered activity and the activity during the driving of the
729 roadways was made up of events with low energy (10^1 and 10^2 J). The effects
730 of tectonic faults (mainly reverse faults - overthrusts) were also recorded
731 during the R&P trial test (see Fig. 13). When roadways are driven near
732 tectonic faults, these faults are activated and a higher number of events are
733 recorded around the faults. Tectonic faults can be activated in the wide area
734 around the roadways that creates pillars (see Fig. 13b). Both the increase in
735 the registered activity around the faults and the activity during the driving
736 of roadways consisted of events with low energy (10^1 and 10^2 J), and rarely
737 of events with energy 10^3 J.

738 Using the denser local seismological network, the Regional Seismic Polyg-
739 onal Network was able to localise most of the main tremors in the area under

740 study. The accuracy of this localisation was estimated to be on the order
741 of metres (or tens of metres at most) in both the horizontal and vertical
742 directions. This was confirmed by *in situ* observations of deformations in the
743 mine workings following other recorded tremors. Despite the fact that the
744 R&P method was used in the very difficult conditions of the USCB, the rock
745 mass was sufficiently homogeneous to transmit seismological waves, even in
746 the presence of old roadways.

747 The major advantage of the seismological system was its non-severity in
748 the need of transferring the stations. The importance of the preparation
749 phase must not be underestimated: if the right locations with minimal an-
750 thropogenic seismic noise are found, and the vertical levels of the locations
751 are also taken into consideration, the ability to localise tremors can be very
752 precise. Data gathering in both cases was conducted automatically, and the
753 final evaluation was made by a geophysicist. If the preparation phase is care-
754 fully conducted, the system can run and gather data on its own for a very
755 long time, and with minimum financial requirements.

756 A detailed analysis of the seismoacoustic observations enabled us to iden-
757 tify situations where the activity showed some small anomalies, which were
758 studied in detail in terms of the natural, mining and geomechanical condi-
759 tions (at the same locations selected for the seismological observations shown
760 in Fig. 8). As the roadways approached previously driven roadways or old
761 mine workings, the activity increased to more than usual; this is most likely
762 to be due to the increased fracture area around the roadways, especially dur-
763 ing the completion of pillars (Fig. 14 and 15). The increase in seismoacoustic
764 activity was measured based on the higher number of registered events. Both
765 the increase in registered activity and the activity during road driving con-
766 sisted of events with low energy (from 10^0 to 10^2 J). The main limitation of
767 this method is connected with the possibility of creating a good location for
768 the basis of investigation, i.e. the locations of geophones in coal seams (due
769 to the existence of previously driven roadways or old roadways).

770 Analyses of the influence of the R&P mining method on the surface were
771 based on direct measurements of the roadway roof subsidence in the R&P
772 panels and measurements of the vertical displacements of control points Nos.
773 1 to 8 and RN 146.1, located on the surface. Based on the measurements
774 made for Panels 1 and 2, and taking into account the tectonic conditions
775 of the location and the total monitoring period for the points, a value of
776 250 mm was accepted for the roadway roof subsidence. The CSM North
777 shaft protection pillar was not designed as fully protective, meaning that the

778 control points that were stabilised immediately around the protected area in
779 the area of the CSM Mine were affected both by R&P mining and by longwall
780 mining in the surroundings of this pillar. The surface subsidence most likely
781 from R&P mining method was estimated based on the differences in the
782 increment of subsidence between individual points along the line of control
783 points Nos. 1 to 8. The most probable value of the surface subsidence due
784 to R&P mining was determined from the difference between control points
785 Nos. 1 and 6 from the measurement made on 02/08/2016. However, this
786 value for the subsidence cannot be considered final, as mining continued until
787 09/2017. The theoretical subsidence at control point No. 6 was determined
788 from a static empirical calculation based on Knothe's method, which gave a
789 value of 17 mm.

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